

Saint Joseph the Worker Church: A Case Study in AI-Enhanced 3D Digitisation and Virtual Reality

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ABSTRACT

This research paper presents a virtual reality visualisation of the interior of the Chapel at Saint Joseph the Worker Church, the youngest Catholic church in Macao, established in 1999. Located in the Iao Hon district near the Gongbei border gate, the church symbolises openness and welcome to the people of China. This study aims to create an interactive user experience to digitally preserve the chapel's architecture, paintings, wood crafts, and statues, aligning with the church's missionary direction towards the Far East. Utilising advanced technologies such as Blender for 3D modelling and AI-driven tools for generating 3D content, this project captures the essence of the chapel's interior with high-resolution photography and precise digital reconstruction. The virtual environment is designed to be accessible via VR headsets and other devices, offering an immersive experience that enhances cultural preservation and evangelisation efforts. This paper also discusses the potential for future developments, including real-time lighting and smooth avatar navigation within the virtual reality space, to further enrich the interactive experience and broaden its reach.

Keywords

Virtual Reality, Cultural Preservation, 3D Visualisation, Digital Archiving, Artificial Intelligence

1 Introduction

Saint Joseph the Worker Church, the youngest Catholic church in Macao, was established in 1999 and locates in

the Iao Hon district, closed to Gongbei boarder gate. Most of the residents in this area are workers and new immigrants from Mainland China. The appearance of the church is like two arms opened towards China, symbolising the welcome to the Chinese people to visit and get to know Christ. Bishop Lam Ka-tseung once said that “the land opposite the church leads directly to the seaside and overlooks the Mainland China like a runway”. The church was built to symbolise its flying to China and the entire coastal area of the Far East, implying that the missionary direction of the Macao Diocese to the Far East. More information about the church—its history, surroundings, photos, and more—can be found at: <https://sjose.catholic.org.mo/> [1].

This purpose of this research is to build a digital visualisation of the interior of the Chapel in the Saint Joseph the Worker Church, to be experience throughout Virtual Reality devices. Celebrating its 25th anniversary last year, this proposal aims to create a VR interactive user experience to digitally preserve its architecture, paintings, wood crafts, and statues.

2 Immersive and Virtual Experiences in Macao

There have not been too many immersive experiences using Virtual Reality in Macao. There are virtual tours captured in panoramic photography like cultural buildings and historical sites from the Government [2, 3,

[4], library tour in University of Macau¹ and Macau Millennium College [5]. The researchers have been working on digitising history and heritage elements around Macao [6, 7] and virtual exhibitions [8]. With other experts and researchers, since Pandemic COVID-19, aiming to broaden connection and coverage of the research outcome internationally.

The Macao Cultural Affairs Bureau launched a virtual recreation project of the church at St. Paul's College [9], a historic site established in 1594 by the Jesuits and significant as the first university in Asia during the Ming Dynasty. Despite enduring multiple fires, the façade remains a cultural icon in Macao. The virtual tour, initiated in December 2022, offers an immersive experience through a temporary installation equipped with VR technology, allowing visitors to explore the church's history and architecture. The initial version featured a guided VR tour with limited interactivity and a mini game focused on conservation tasks, though it faced challenges such as language barriers and audiovisual technical limitations. An upgraded version introduced in March 2023 enhanced the experience with improved visuals, additional language options, and new features like a "crab dance" and a parade of iconic statues. External features, including a WeChat mini-programme and augmented reality experiences, further enriched the visit. However, the upgrade also highlighted issues like rushed exploration due to time constraints and inconsistent information delivery across different languages and platforms. Overall, while the immersive experience at the Ruins of Saint Paul offers a unique blend of education and entertainment, there remains room for improvement in terms of interactivity and information coherence [10].

Other local business like the Bright Dawn Studio, is also keen on creating 3D models and miniatures of local cultural elements like, St. Paul's Ruins, Pui Ching Middle School, Holy House of Mercy, St. Dominic's Church, etc. These models are, mostly, exterior².

¹ <https://vr.library.um.edu.mo>

² https://www.instagram.com/the_bright_dawn_studio/

3 Virtual Environment Recreation

Open-source 3D modelling application, Blender 4.4.3³ was operated on MacOS. In collaboration with the Parish Priest, the detailed architecture plans, both bird view and elevation, were used as the reference of the construction of the 3D model. These architectural plans were imported directly to the orthographic views within the viewport which provides realistic ratio to the 3D modeller without the need to measure several locations that are unreachable. Reference photos of important details (Figure 1) and notes were taken to ensure the authenticity of the models.

Figure 1: Interior of the Chapel (Photograph by the Authors)

Figure 2: 3D model of the interior of the Chapel

³ <https://www.blender.org>

Figure 3: Mystery of Salvation and Stations of Way of Cross in the Chapel (Photographs by the authors)

Figure 4: Workflow from photos to AI (3DAiStudio) to 3D models (Photographs by the authors)

The researchers first created the basic architecture of the chapel as the foundation, putting recurring items, e.g. wall lamps, stained glass windows, painting frames of the Mystery of Salvation, benches, etc. (Figure 2) Then, windows, doors were modelled along with wood crafted stations of the Way of Cross.

Both the painting set, and the Stations were captured in professional photographic settings. Due to the dim lighting and shadows on-site, The Sony A7R III is a high-resolution full-frame camera optimised for still life reproduction. It was paired with the Tamron 150-500mm F/5-6.7 Di III VC VXD zoom lens - a telephoto optic with exceptional resolving power ideal for capturing distant wall-mounted sculptures and oil paintings while emphasising subject details.

The Fujifilm GFX 50S II, a medium format camera renowned for its outstanding dynamic range and colour accuracy, delivers faithful reproduction of artwork textures, tonal gradations, and spatial ambiance within the venue. It was equipped with:

- The GF 35-70mm f/4.5-5.6 WR zoom lens: a compact yet powerful optic producing high-resolution images across diverse compositions, perfectly suited for both close-up documentation and environmental framing.
- The Laowa 19mm f/2.8 Zero-D: one of the smallest lenses in its class. Despite its minimalist construction, this lens captures an incredible 110° angle of view with virtually zero distortion.

For stability during long exposures and bracketed shots, the system was mounted on a Gitzo GK-2545T carbon fiber tripod providing exceptional vibration dampening.

Precise compositional control was achieved using the Leofoto G4 Geared Head, enabling fine three-axis adjustments even within confined spaces. This setup was critical in maintaining alignment across multiple exposures for later HDR blending.

Given the low-light conditions, exposure bracketing was employed to capture a broad dynamic range. In post-processing, Lightroom was operated for HDR merging and precise colour correction, aiming to faithfully reproduce the original tones and textures of the paintings. White balance and sharpness were adjusted meticulously to ensure the resulting images could serve both archival and academic purposes.

Figure 5: VR tour of the chapel on Kuula (Photograph by the authors)

These high-resolution paintings captured were directly UV mapped to the 3D model with a semi-smooth texture base. While the Stations of Way of Cross were sent to an online 3D generative artificial intelligence named 3DAiStudio⁴ to achieve basic 3D sculptures (Figure 4).

After these above-mentioned elements are in place, photorealistic panoramic renderings are captured for the VR experience setup.

4 Virtual Tour Apparatus

The virtual reality (Figure 5) is streamed on Kuula.co⁵ which Meta Quest Pro is recommended for the experience. Users can also navigate around the tour with a smartphone, tablet, or laptop for semi-immersive experience. Users can navigate the VR by interacting with the arrow hotspots on the floor and take a detailed

look at the artefacts with those camera icons on the top rights of statues, sculptures and paintings.

This virtual tour does not only allow self-navigation within the space, but it also accommodates unlimited individual and group access. Offering quasi-realistic immersive experience with only higher resolution to images and details. This detailed information about artefacts – paintings, architects, sculptures, etc. is a potential for Edutainment and Gamification.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

The 3D virtual environment was built not only to digitally and interactively archive the interior elements of the chapel. It also assisted in consideration of reallocating the organ piano. The organ piano was originally positioned in the front right of the chapel next to the altar and it was proposed to move to the back of

⁴ <https://www.3daistudio.com/>

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<https://kuula.co/share/collection/7D7tk?logo=0&info=1&fs=1&vr=1&d=1&thumbs=1>

the hall along with the opportunity to upgrade and update the entire sound system. Nevertheless, it is too heavy to move without a concrete idea that the adjustment would be in favour of the organist, the choir conductor, the choir and the officiating priest. Thus, this 3D simulation came in picture. All 3D models in the scene were built in real scale, and thus, allow us to have a realistic rendering simulation. This can save both time and expenses for attempting the reallocation in case the outcome was not desirable which helps facilitating the administrative aspect of the parish.

To make this a truly interactive experience, we target to import the 3D model into a game developing engine, Unreal Engine for achieving real time light and smooth avatar navigation to the virtual reality. It will also be promoted to the Parish new official website and its social media accounts like Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp community to achieve large social coverage. We will also promote this interactive user experience to the Parish for an installation for people to experience with the Meta Quest Pro. Nevertheless, it would be ideal if this experience can reach to communities abroad as it aims to evangelise.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Acknowledgement to the Saint Joseph the Worker Church, its Parish Priest and Secretary, for the unconditional support and trust along the way. It has been a time-consuming process but also a dream come true to make possible a seamless integration of tradition and modern, as well as manual technique and artificial intelligence assistance.

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